

SUPPORTER

**Roadmap towards the
development of a 4I-GEP,
State University of Physical
Education and Sport
(SUPES)**

The first version of the SUPES roadmap

This document is the first version of the State University of Physical Education and Sport (SUPES) to develop an inclusive, innovative, intersectional and impactful gender equality plan (4I-GEP). It has been developed within the context of their participation in the SUPPORTER project by the SUPES team, with the support of SUPPORTER's expert partners. The full text, as well as other partners' roadmaps, are to be found in SUPPORTER's deliverable: [D4.1 Report on the design of the institutional roadmaps.](#)

Authors: Elena Mocrousov, Natalia Nastas, Liliana Budevici-Puiu.

Please cite as Mocrousov, E., Nastas, N., Budevici-Puiu, L. (2023). Roadmap towards the development of a 4IGEP. SUPPORTER Project.

Acknowledgement and disclaimer

Funded by
the European Union

This roadmap has been developed within SUPPORTER, a project funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.

SUPPORTER: find out more!

<https://supporter-project.eu/>

[company/gep-supporter-project/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/gep-supporter-project/)

[@GEP_SUPPORTER](https://twitter.com/GEP_SUPPORTER)

[GepSupporterProject](https://www.facebook.com/GepSupporterProject)

Introduction

The SUPPORTER project aims to foster gender-related, **sustainable**, and **transformative** institutional changes in sports higher education institutions paying specific attention to the challenge of **gender-based violence and leading to the development of inclusive, innovative, intersectional and impactful gender equality plans (4I-GEPs)**.

The transformation of existing institutional GEPs into 4I-GEPs is achieved through the co-design and implementation of individual roadmaps, tailored to the needs of each implementing organisation.

This document outlines the development and implementation of the roadmap of the State University of Physical Education and Sport (SUPES) within the SUPPORTER project. **It describes the grounding actions to be taken and the individual steps to be followed.**

The SUPES roadmap encompasses a set of Grounding Actions (GAs) to be implemented from March 2024 to June 2025. These actions address mandatory and recommended thematic GEP elements ([Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans](#)) under-addressed in the IO's existing institutional GEP. Critical challenges, including engagement and participation barriers in implementing the roadmaps, resource limitations and organisational resistance, have been identified, alongside measures to effectively address them.

The roadmap represents a tailored strategy, responsive to the unique needs and opportunities within SUPES, structured in a set of Grounding Actions which are going to be carried out within a 16-month implementation period (March 2024 – June 2025). It is crucial to emphasise that, while carefully designed, the roadmap is a living document, likely to undergo several adjustments to effectively address evolving challenges and time constraints and feedback gathered during the organisation of the planned activities. This shall ensure that the roadmap remains relevant and conducive to transformative change through the development, at the end of this period, of the new 4I-GEPs.

Development of institutional roadmaps

A roadmap is a detailed document that sets the steps and actions (a.k.a grounding actions) necessary to achieve institutional changes into a common strategic framework and timeframe and has the key features of being flexible and progressive.

In the context of SUPPORTER, a roadmap provides a clear and detailed plan of grounding actions that will foster the institutional changes needed to pave the way for the development of the 4I-GEP.

After national and institutional mapping and self-assessment of the existing GEP and institutional policies, the SUPES team co-designed their roadmap with their internal stakeholders and the support of the SUPPORTER mentoring team from December 2023 to March 2024. This participatory approach ensured that the roadmap addressed specific problems in the institution and tailored it to the needs of sports higher education.

Steps

The co-design of the institutional roadmaps consisted of five steps:

1. Launch of the co-design process: The roadmap concept, as well as the scope and objectives of institutional roadmaps, were introduced to SUPES.
2. Internal consultation process: Meetings were held with different types of internal stakeholders in a consultation process that led to the first draft of the institutional roadmaps
3. Consultation with the mentoring team: SUPES participated in consultation meetings with the mentoring team, which consisted of consortium experts.
4. Internal review process: SUPES reviewed the roadmap internally to address any previously identified challenges and gaps.
5. Finalization of the roadmap.

Figure 1 – Steps to co-design partners' roadmaps within SUPPORTER

SUPES: the organisation

The State University of Physical Education and Sport is an integral part of the state higher didactic education in the Republic of Moldova that since 2005 has joined the Movement of University Education Reforma and its integration into the European Academic Environment that was recently completed by signing of the Magna Charta Universitatum. The university curricula are aimed at the initial training at the 1st level of education- License and professional/scientific training, at the 2nd level – Master's Studies, and at the 3rd level – PhD Studies and Post-doctorate.

An important event for our institution was the Decree of the President of the Republic of Moldova no.771-IV from 21.09.2006, Vladimir Voronin, regarding the reorganisation of the National Institute of Physical Education and Sport into the State University of Physical Education and Sport.

In this context, the State University of Physical Education and Sport defines its mission through its 14 chairs, scientific laboratories subordinated to the Scientific Centre. The SUPES has also one scientific journal: "Physical Culture Science", therefore over 250 lecturers have the possibility to publish the results of their scientific research.

Today the number of students has risen to 3000 students at three faculties: Physical Education and Sport, Kinetotherapy, Protection, guard and security and Department of Professional Continuous Training (specialities: Physical Education; Coaching activities; Sports leadership; Fitness and recreation programmes; Kinetotherapy and occupational therapy; Hotel, tourism and leisure, Civil and public security; Rescuers and fire-fighters, Border security) and nine master's degree programmes.

The technical and material base of the university consists of two study blocks with a capacity of 4876 m², two sports complexes with a capacity of 5295 m², 19 laboratories, 15 sports halls, a swimming pool with a capacity of 4036 m², one tennis court, a mini-football court and other strategic facilities that contribute to the training of good sports specialists in the general field of studies: *011 Education, 1000 Science of sports, 101 Personal services, 103 Security services.*

Gender equality in SUPES

Mandatory process-related elements

Public document

The GEP of the State University of Physical Education and Sport from the Republic of Moldova was signed by the Rector, it was published on the website, and it has been communicated with all the faculties.

Roadmap towards the development of a 4I-GEP

The context

The *vision* of the State University of Physical Education and Sport is to be a leader in education and scientific research in the field of physical culture and sport in the Republic of Moldova, to be identified among the reference institutions at the European level in the achievement, training and development of professional skills, abilities necessary for a successful professional path.

The *mission* of the State University of Physical Education and Sport is to carry out research and education at national and international standards of excellence.

Diversity and inclusion are core values of the State University of Physical Education and Sport. SUPES is open to everyone who wishes to study or work here. We are an open community in which anyone who wishes to contribute to the University's ambitions and all that we stand for is welcome and will enjoy equal opportunities.

Our community is diverse in many ways: we differ from one another in terms of ethnicity, gender, ability and health, religion, age, socio-economic background and more. SUPES wants to be an open community where all students and staff feel at home. To allow diversity to flourish, our university has to be truly inclusive. SUPES has a societal responsibility to create a learning and working environment in which everyone can develop their talents to their full potential. An essential condition for achieving excellent academic education and research is an inclusive academic community.

Gender equality has been a central focus of SUPES diversity policy since we were with SUPPORTER. At the same time, we recognise that our identities and experiences are composed of multiple dimensions, and we still have a lot of work requiring an intersectional approach. To promote gender equality, we need to take into account the intersections between, inter alia, gender, social class, ethnicity and race, sexual orientation, and health and ability. Gender equality can only be successfully promoted if the diversity of gender identities and their intersectionality is addressed. SUPES diversity policy therefore does not exclusively focus on gender but promotes gender equality as part of an integrated and intersectional approach which fosters diversity, equity and inclusion for all staff and students.

Aims and Objectives

a. Diversity is about how our student and staff population bring different experiences, ideas and perspectives. The SUPES aims to reflect the diversity of Moldavian society, including in areas such as ethnicity, gender, ability and health, religion, age and socio-economic background.

b. Inclusion shifts the focus from the individual and the representation of specific groups to the institution and the culture of the learning and working environment. Specifically, inclusion means not just being diverse, but giving equal opportunities to everyone and ensuring everyone feels at home, regardless of their background. This, with a climate where inclusion is the norm, is a basic requirement for success. An inclusive university is a learning and working environment where everyone can fully develop their talents and is supported by the institutions, staff and students in doing so.

Key goals

The GEP sets out and implements the SUPES policy in the long term. Specific policy areas are concretized and given shape in the form of a range of activities and projects on the central as well as faculty levels.

The key goals of the GEP SUPES policy are:

- To promote an inclusive learning environment through inclusive curricula, lectures and pedagogy

- To promote diversity (in the areas of gender, disability and ethnic and cultural diversity) among staff members in all positions. To promote diversity expertise and inclusive leadership among all staff members.
- To promote diversity of applicants and an inclusive approach to research.
- Promotion of knowledge and understanding of the various themes that touch on GEP expertise in key roles and facilitating the development of expertise in administrators, staff and teaching staff are important principles for promoting an inclusive learning and working environment.
- The creation of structures that provide clear frameworks for consciously promoting diversity and inclusion in the form of guidelines, agreements and procedures designed to safeguard diversity and inclusion, and promote positive change.
- Cultural change. This requires a change in perspectives and behaviour. Reflection, dialogue and collaboration are key components of initiating and supporting concrete change that fosters diversity and inclusion as part of our institutional culture.
- Permanent integration. This ensures that the GEP policy is firmly anchored within the organisation. This entails both capacity and expertise in key roles at different levels of the organisation. In addition to committed administrators, experts and policy officers, and staff and student networks in the area of GEP, there must be staff members at the faculty, department and institute level who can facilitate and promote policy and its implementation.

Structure of the roadmap

<i>Period of implementation</i>	<i>Grounding actions/Action lines</i>	<i>GEP element</i>
PROJECT PERIOD	GA1 – Raising awareness on gender equality and the GEP	Training Public document Work-life balance and organisational culture
	GA2 – Development of a communication strategy for external stakeholder engagement	Resources
	GA3 – Setting up a GE Committee at the institutional/faculty level	Resources
	GA4 – Raising Awareness of gender inequalities in the sports environments	Training
	GA5 – Establishing a gender audit and monitoring mechanism	Data collection and monitoring Gender balance in decision-making

		GE in recruitment
	GA6 – Establishing Internal Structures and Procedures for GBV Prevention and Treatment within the Institution	Resources Measures against GBV
	GA7 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders	Training Measures against GBV
4I – GEP		
IMPLEMENTATION PERIOD	To be developed at the end of the SUPPORTER project, based on the lessons learnt from the roadmaps and the newly developed 4I-GEP of the institution.	
SUSTAINABILITY PERIOD		

The Grounding Actions

A set of seven Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5	GA6	GA7
<i>Intersectional</i>	x				x	x	x
<i>Innovative</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>Inclusive</i>	x	x	x		x	x	
<i>Impactful</i>		x		x		x	x
<i>Tailored to sports</i>			x	x		x	x

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender equality and the role of GEP in the promotion of a gender-inclusive culture with the University

GA1 is focused on an awareness-raising campaign, consisting of various activities to increase understanding of the basic concepts of gender equality and of the importance of GEP as an integral tool in promoting institutional change.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising; Public document

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture

b. Objectives

As the first Grounding Action of this roadmap, GA1 aims to set the baseline for the following actions by pursuing the following objectives:

- To get the topic of gender equality on the institution's agenda
- To promote a uniform understanding of the concept of gender+ equality
- To explain the role of the GEP in promoting gender+ equality and institutional change

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up a working group for this GA. Besides the SUPPORTER project team, the working group includes a) the HR Department which is currently responsible for implementing the GEP, b) student and staff representatives (in order to better understand the target groups' level of awareness and needs), c) members of the Communications Department which will be responsible for designing the material of the awareness-raising campaign and d) external consultants, if needed, to support the development of the campaign. The different tasks under this GA will be allocated among the working group members. Once formed, this group will be responsible for the design and implementation of the campaign.
2. Development of the awareness-raising campaign, which includes the following:
 - Establishing the campaign's objectives, namely to challenge the current institutional culture by increasing knowledge on the basic concepts of gender equality and by introducing and explaining the role of the GEP.
 - Defining the target audience (students, academic and administrative staff, external stakeholders)
 - Setting the budget, indicatively taking into account the human resources that may be needed (either internally or for the involvement of external experts if there is no gender expertise in the university), the costs of communication material and the venues where the different activities will take place).
 - Outlining the campaign's activities and timeframe. Indicatively, the following activities shall be implemented:
 - One info-day for students of all levels to discuss basic concepts regarding gender equality and to highlight the role of the GEP
 - One info-session for academic and administrative staff to clarify the basic concepts of gender equality, explain the role of the GEP and highlight all efforts undertaken within the SUPPORTER project, including the results and planned actions, in order to promote institutional change
 - Determining the campaign's outcomes, including the definition of clear and achievable results and indicators and tools to achieve them (e.g. feedback form for participants, pre/post-session questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge of the participants)

3. Design of the campaign's material, including the preparation of the campaign's material (posters, social media/website posts, presentations) and the use of appropriate communication channels for engaging the target groups
4. Finalising the campaign and seeking approval from the senior management
5. Implementation of the planned activities
6. Evaluation of the campaign's impact through feedback from participants and assessment of increased knowledge via a pre- and post-workshop questionnaire.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Senior management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Student Union	Consulting
Department of Communication	Co-producing
External experts	Consulting/Co-producing

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited human resources leading to difficulties in forming a working group • Lack of internal expertise in developing the campaign • Reluctance of students or staff to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics. • Lack of interest in participating in workshops. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear allocation of tasks to avoid overload or confusion of the working group • Engagement of external experts for the development and implementation • Developing (and communicating) a clear description of the content and objectives of the workshops and panel discussions. • Consider integrating it into existing sets of activities (e.g. induction week)

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Communications Department External experts Student Union	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024

	Staff representatives			
2. Development of awareness-raising campaign	Working group (as formed in the previous step)	Detailed plan	Human resources	April – May 2024
3. Design of the awareness-raising campaign	Working group	Communication material Material for the awareness-raising activities (e.g. presentations for info-sessions)	Multimedia tools Human resources	May – June 2024
4. Seeking approval	Working group Senior management	Approved awareness-raising plan	Human resources	June 2024
5. Launching the awareness-raising activities: - one info-day for students - one info-day for staff	Working group External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	July – September 2024
6. Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)	Human resources	September 2024

GA2 – Development of a communication strategy for external stakeholder engagement

This GA builds an effective communication strategy and channels that cover the various dimensions of gender+ equality and focuses on external stakeholder engagement at local, national and international levels.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources; Training and awareness-raising

b. Objectives

This action aims to help develop a robust communication strategy to shift institutional attention to the gender dimension and increase outreach efforts to advance the values of inclusiveness and gender equality in the local ecosystem. This translates into the following objectives:

- To increase the visibility of university efforts to induce institutional change through the promotion of gender-sensitive initiatives
- To establish effective communication channels for internal and external stakeholder engagement
- To disseminate the results of the SUPPORTER and other projects and attract new collaborations
- To attract new collaborations with frontline actors in the sports environment

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up the working group. Besides the SUPPORTER project team, the Communications Department will be largely involved in this action. (incl. comms, students and/or staff) and clearly allocating tasks for building the communication strategy and the design of the awareness-raising plan
2. Defining the communication strategy's short-term and long-term goals, tools and target audiences (internal and external stakeholders). This stage also identifies the existing communication channels and explores their effectiveness in pursuing the defined goals.
3. Development of the communication strategy, indicatively including the capitalisation of existing and the establishment of new channels (such as email exchanges, university events, seminars, and departmental meetings) and the creation of a toolkit with communication and dissemination material.
4. Seeking approval for the finalised communication strategy (if necessary)
5. As part of the communication strategy, create an InfoPoint within the University's website to serve as a repository for all resources and activities related to gender equality (e.g. GEP and related policies, legal and institutional framework, SUPPORTER activities and outcomes).

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Communications Department	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Students/Staff	Informing
HR	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges in choosing appropriate communication channels and ensuring their effectiveness Limited human resources Lack of permission for the creation of the info-point within the website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Replacing traditional communication methods with innovative channels (e.g. expanding the use of social media). Testing the channels before finalising the strategy could also help identify such issues in advance.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Communications department	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024
2. Development of communication strategy	Working group	Communication strategy document	Human resources	April – May 2024
3. Design of the communication tools	Working group	Communication tools/material	Multimedia tools Human resources	May 2024
4. Seeking approval	Project team Senior management	Approved strategy	Human resources	June 2024
5. Creating the InfoPoint	Working group IT support	Operational website/space	Human resources Software	May – June 2024

		within the faculty's website		
--	--	------------------------------	--	--

GA3 – Setting up a GE Committee at the institutional/faculty level

This Grounding Action sees to the creation of a GE body at the faculty mandated with the management of gender issues through the implementation of the GEP.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

b. Objectives

- To establish an independent body for the management of gender-related matters within the institution through the implementation of the 4I-GEP
- To increase gender expertise within the faculty, with a focus on gender issues in sports environments
- To establish accountability for the implementation and update of the 4I-GEP within the institution/faculty
- To ensure clear task allocation and smooth cooperation among institutional bodies with a similar mandate

c. Implementation plan

1. Geo members, as well as the frequency, duration and whereabouts of the Committee's meetings.
2. Appointment of the Committee's members following internal placement procedures (to reduce the need for further resources in case of external recruitment)
3. Identifying the training needs of the Committee members on gender+ equality through discussion with external GE experts
4. Training for the Committee members according to identified needs
5. Internal communication of the new Committee and forging links with relevant institutional bodies to communicate their role and discuss effective ways for collaboration

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Co-producing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Student/Staff	Informing

Legal Department	Consulting
HR	Consulting
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of available university staff to assume the Committee's responsibilities Overlapping mandates of different bodies Resistance at management level due to lack of awareness/reluctance to allocate resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Call for applications-Job opening (in case financial resources are available) Clear allocation of tasks discussed and decided at the management level One-on-one meetings between the SUPPORTER project team and the management in order to explain in detail the importance of a dedicated body on gender equality

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Review of existing bodies and responsibilities	Project team	List of existing bodies with gender-related tasks	Human resources	September 2024
2. Formulating the GE Committee's mandate	Project team Ethics Committee Legal Department	Document with mandate Established internal structures and capacity pool	Human resources	October 2024
3. Defining the Committee's operational details	Project team Legal Department HR	Set of criteria for commission's selection	Human resources	October – November 2024
4. Appointment of Committee members	HR Legal Department	List of Committee's members and roles	Human resources	November 2024
5. Identifying training needs	Project team GE Committee External experts	Report on knowledge gaps after meeting with GE experts	Human resources External expertise	November – December 2024
6. Training of Committee members	Project team Ethics Committee External experts	Training material; Increased knowledge	Human resources	January – February 2025

7. Internal communication of the Committee's creation and mandate	GE Committee Deans and Heads of Departments Ethics Committee	Satisfactory degree of internal communication	Institutional departments (heads and active department members) Communicators with external stakeholders	March 2025
--	--	---	---	------------

GA4 – Raising Awareness of gender inequalities in the sports environments

This GA focuses on fostering a better understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases in the academic sports environment through a set of awareness-raising activities.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

b. Objectives

- To integrate discussions on unconscious bias, stereotypes, and the implications of gender inequality on individuals and the broader sports community.
- To empower female athletes by challenging the perception that certain sports are destined for men and encouraging gender-balanced involvement in sports, promoting the idea that talent and skills are not limited to gender.
- To tackle gender stereotypes beyond the selection of sports, including the gender of coaches and the myth of meritocracy behind leadership positions and career progression

c. Implementation plan

1. Setting up a working group for this GA. Besides the SUPPORTER project team, the working group should include a) the HR Department which is currently responsible for implementing the GEP, b) student and staff representatives (in order to better understand the target groups' level of awareness and needs), c) members of the Communications Department which will be responsible for designing the material of the awareness-raising campaign and d) external consultants, if needed, to support the development of the campaign. The different tasks under this GA will be clearly allocated among the working group members. Once formed, this group will be responsible for the design and implementation of the campaign.
2. Development of the awareness-raising campaign, which includes the following:
 - Establishing the campaign's objectives, namely to challenge the current institutional culture by increasing knowledge on the basic concepts of gender equality and by introducing and explaining the role of the GEP.
 - Defining the target audience (students, academic and administrative staff, external stakeholders)
 - Setting the budget, indicatively taking into account the human resources that may be needed (either internally or for the involvement of external experts if there is no gender

- expertise in the university), the costs of communication material and the venues where the different activities will take place).
- Outlining the campaign's activities and timeframe. Indicatively, the following activities shall be implemented: a) Two thematic workshops/Panel discussions with staff/students, b) One local stakeholder event to engage external stakeholders in a discussion about gender stereotypes in sports and how to tackle them.
 - Determining the campaign's outcomes, including the definition of clear and achievable results and indicators and tools to achieve them (e.g. feedback form for participants, pre/post-session questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge of the participants)
3. Design of the campaign's material, including the preparation of the campaign's material (posters, social media/website posts, presentations) and the use of appropriate communication channels for engaging the target groups
 4. Finalising the campaign and seeking approval from the senior management
 5. Implementation of the planned activities
 6. Evaluation of the campaign's impact through feedback from participants and assessment of increased knowledge via a pre- and post-workshop questionnaire.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Senior management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Student Union	Consulting
Department of Communication	Co-producing
External experts	Consulting/Co-producing

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited human resources leading to difficulties in forming a working group ● Lack of internal expertise in developing the campaign ● Reluctance of students or staff to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics. ● Lack of interest of external stakeholders to participate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clear allocation of tasks to avoid overload or confusion of the working group ● Engagement of external experts for the development and implementation ● Developing (and communicating) a clear description of the content and objectives of the workshops and panel discussions. ● Using the new communication strategy, invest efforts in networking and capitalise on existing collaborations to prepare impactful local events. Co-organisation of the event with an influential actor will be considered.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Communications Department External experts Student Union Staff representatives	List of team members	Human resources	September 2024
2. Development of awareness-raising campaign	Working group (as formed in the previous step)	Detailed plan	Human resources	October 2024
3. Design of the awareness-raising campaign	Working group	Communication material and material for the awareness-raising activities (e.g. presentations for info-sessions)	Multimedia tools Human resources	October – November 2024
4. Seeking approval	Working group Senior management	Approved awareness-raising plan	Human resources	November 2024
5. Launching the awareness-raising activities	Working group External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	December 2024 – February 2025
6. Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms	Human resources	February 2025

Level of
engagement with
campaign content
(e.g. likes, shares,
comments)

GA5 – Establishing a gender audit and monitoring mechanism

This Grounding Action aims to create a gender audit and monitoring system and pilot the new data collection processes in a selected area of priority.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring

Thematic: Gender balance in leadership and decision-making; Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

b. Objectives

- To construe a comprehensive image regarding the organisation's and faculty's current datasets related to gender equality
- To conduct a needs assessment and analysis of the state of play in the institution
- To adopt a holistic approach in gender audit which includes the collection of qualitative and quantitative data, addresses aspects of intersectionality and considers the sports context

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this GA:

1. Creation of a working group and assignment of roles in a clear manner to capitalise on relevant expertise and avoid confusion in task implementation.
2. Review and analysis of existing datasets at the University to map what is already being collected. Focus is placed on methods, competent body and frequency of the gender audit. Identification of gender data gaps.
3. Defining suitable data collection and analysis methods and responsible institutional body. Selection of a suitable repository tool and defining the frequency of progress monitoring. Identification of criteria for the recruitment of participants
4. Development of tools for data collection on the two selected thematic areas, making sure to incorporate intersectional and sports-sensitive aspects. Both quantitative (e.g. statistical information and questionnaire) and qualitative (e.g. focus groups, interview) methods will be used and different target groups will be identified. External consultation may be needed at this stage.
5. Carrying out a pilot round of the defined data collection processes (e.g. survey and focus group) on this specific thematic area.
6. Analysis of the collected data and report on findings.
7. Reflection upon the efficiency of the selected tools and refinement for future use.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Consulting
Ethics Committee	Co-producing
Student/Staff	Informing
HR	Consulting
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of understanding Low engagement (due to limited time, inadequate efforts for the recruitment of participants, little interest in GE, and reluctance to share views) Internal resistances (to identify the need or value of a gender audit or to give prominence to latent inequalities) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing (and communicating) a clear description of the objectives of the data collection Clear compliance with GDPR is explained in the information sheet and consent form accompanying the questionnaire/interview guide The preceding GA1 will raise awareness on the topic and importance of GE and create the basis for the successful implementation of this action

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Ethics Committee HR	List of group members	Human resources	September 2024
2. Review and analysis of existing datasets	Working group	List of identified gaps	Human resources Software	October 2024
3. Defining data collection, analysis and recruitment methods/tools	Working group	Methodological plan for the collection and analysis of data List of recruitment criteria and	Human resources	October – November 2024

		recruitment methods		
4. Development of data collection tools	Working group External experts	Interview guide and/or Questionnaire	Human resources Consultation time with experts	November 2024
5. Pilot round of data collection	Working group	Number of respondents/participants Number of interviews Feedback from personal meetings and focus groups	Human resources Communication tools for recruiting participants Venue Software	December 2024 – January 2025
6. Data analysis	Working group	Report on findings	Human resources	February 2025
7. Assessment and refinement of employed tools	Working group	Number of respondents Quality/sufficiency of collected data	Human resources	March 2025

GA6 – Establishing internal structures and procedures for GBV prevention and treatment within the institution

This Grounding Action consists of the development of a Protocol for preventing and addressing GBV incidents at the University and the establishment of the necessary structures for the implementation of the Protocol.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- Development of a comprehensive protocol for preventing and addressing GBV cases within the faculty.
- Definition of gender-based violence content and fundamental principles regarding reporting of relevant incidents
- Creation of a culture of zero tolerance towards gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this GA:

1. Thorough assessment of existing policies and practices related to GBV prevention and treatment and of their alignment with the national and European legislation.
2. Identification and appointment of a competent body for handling reports on GBV incidents. This could involve the creation of a new body (e.g. a person of trust) or the delegation of these tasks to existing bodies (e.g. Ethics Committee or the newly established GE Committee)
3. Development of the Protocol, which shall include: a) scope and guiding principles, b) prevention measures, c) reporting procedures, d) support services within and outside the University, e) investigation procedures, and f) violation consequences.
4. Seeking approval of the new GBV Protocol and related procedures.
5. Training of persons/Committee members in charge of implementing the protocol on what is gender-based violence and its specificities, for example, understanding trauma and implementing a victim-centred approach.
6. Preparation for the implementation of the Protocol - Establishment of the stipulated procedures.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Senior management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Legal Department	Consulting
IT Department	Co-producing
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance in admitting that GBV is an important issue and of the urgency to adopt measures for preventing and combatting such cases • Limited resources (financial, human, time) for developing and maintaining internal structures and procedures. • Potential legal or regulatory constraints in establishing certain procedures. • Reluctance of management to allocate resources for a new procedure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-on-one meetings between the SUPPORTER project team and the management in order to explain in detail the extent of GBV and the alarming numbers of unreported cases worldwide, combined with compounding vulnerabilities in the sports context • Appointment of the GE Committee or the Ethics Committee as the competent body for handling GBV cases (instead of external recruitment)

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Assessment of existing policies/priorities	Project team Legal Department Ethics Committee	Summary of existing policies/gaps	Human resources	October 2024
2. Appointment of competent body	Project team Legal Department Ethics Committee	New position Description of responsibilities	Human resources Financial resources for the new position (if necessary)	November 2024
3. Development of the Protocol	Project team Ethics Committee External experts (if necessary)	Protocol document	Human resources	November – December 2024
4. Seek approval for the new Protocol	Project team Senior management	Approved Protocol- new reporting mechanism	Human resources	January 2025
5. Training of the competent body for GBV incidents	Project team External expertise	Participation in the training session	Human resources Financial resources for capacity-building in external training	January – March 2025
6. Establishment of new procedures	Project team IT team Communications Department	New structures in place and operational	Human resources Software/technological equipment	February – April 2025

GA7 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

This grounding action develops and implements awareness-raising activities on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environments both at the university and at the local/national level.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- To increase understanding both of internal and of external stakeholders on forms of gender-based violence (physical, sexual, psychological, economic and financial, sexual harassment, online) in the sports context
- To create a safe environment and a culture of respect, equality and zero tolerance towards gender-based violence
- To introduce staff and students to the relevant regulatory framework and internal procedures in place (reporting and case management, support mechanisms) in a simple and comprehensive manner

c. Implementation plan

The following activities will be carried out to implement this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up the working team (incl. students and/or staff, and a communication team to engage external stakeholders effectively)
2. Development of a comprehensive scheme (Define objectives and message, target audience, timeframe and budget, outline the campaign’s activities and desired outcome)
3. Design the material for the planned activities (define appropriate channels, create the visuals, prepare the presentations)
4. Launching the awareness-raising activities. This includes: a) 1 workshop organised for staff, b) 1 workshop organised for students and c) 1 local stakeholder event to raise awareness of targeted external stakeholders such as sports clubs, trainers, associations, umbrella organisations, and public authorities.
5. Evaluate the scheme’s impact and explore the possibility of future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Communications Department	Co-producing
GE Committee	Co-producing
Student Union	Consulting
Mid-level management	Informing
External experts	Consulting/Co-producing

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reluctance of staff and students to attend the training and workshops • Lack of interest from younger students • Difficulty in engaging external stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing (and communicating) a clear description of the content and objectives of the training and workshops • For freshly enrolled students -making the workshop obligatory as the first introductory class at the beginning of the academic year. • Co-organisation of the external event with a key external collaborator (e.g. sports association, the National Olympic Committee)

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Setting up the working group	Project team GBV body Communications department Student Union Staff representatives	List of group members	Human resources	January 2025
2. Development of awareness-raising scheme	Working group	Detailed plan	Human resources	January – February 2025
3. Design of the awareness-raising scheme	Working group	Communication material Material for the awareness-raising activities	Multimedia tools, Human resources.	February 2025
4. Launching the awareness-raising activities	Working group External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources Venue	March-May 2025

		communication tools	Financial resources for guest speakers	
5. Evaluating impact	Project team	<p>Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire</p> <p>Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms</p> <p>Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)</p>	Human resources	June 2025

General timeline

